

Franziska Baumann

The Echo I Touch

Performance

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

The Echo I Touch

Solo Concert for Voice & Sensor Live Electronic
De- & Embodiment in spatial Vocal Performance Art
Franziska Baumann

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Abstract

Franziska Baumann's solo concert reflects relations between embodied acoustic voice and disembodied spatialized voices by means of gestural communication via SensorGlove interface. The interface between her as a singer and the performing system is part of an integrated system which serves communication. Spatially expressed gestures and the sound processes coupled to them allow for many relationships of vocal embodiments and disembodiments and open up multi-layered staging categories and parameters of gestures controlling vocal sound or compositional parameters. Benders, accelerators, gyroscope and ultra-sonic sensors connect the real world of physical phenomena and gestures via serial port to the computer. To a certain extent the specific characteristics of sensors and their respective expressiveness ask for certain gestures. The singer is free to add additional meaning through gesture communication. This interplay of "necessary movements" and communication of ideas through music and gestures opens up various artistic perspectives on body sculptures in movement and sound, an esthetic of a hybrid emerges. The sensor glove becomes a costume, a prop, a visual performance in itself, which can cause different expectations and bewilderment among the audience. Unlike wireless applications, it communicates a specific presence and technological expression.

The music follows a precomposed dramaturgy but is played with an improvisational attitude exploring the interplay between acoustic voice, precomposed sound ideas and live processing with Ambisonic spatialization. The transformation of the sound through processing and spatialization are at times specific (e.g. linked to a direct gesture) and other autonomous (e.g. the machine makes random or precomposed decisions.)

SensorGlove and Mapping

The mappings are made in STEIM's software JunXion and mix up several possibilities in combinations:

- One to one relationships: Fixed assignments of control and result are designed one-dimensionally.

- Diverging: One gesture is assigned to several parameters. A one-dimensional input is split into numerous results.
- Converging: Many gestures are assigned to one parameter. The multidimensional input is mapped onto only one output parameter.
- Multimapping: several gestures are assigned to several parameters at the same time

Background

As "artist in residence" at the STEIM "Studio for Electro Instrumental Music", Amsterdam, Franziska Baumann developed 2001 the first SensorLab based glove with built-in sensors. Together with Andreas Litmanowitsch, an electronics engineer in Bern, she developed 2015 the current version of the SensorGlove Interface. During an Artist Residency at ICST (Institute for Computer Music) in Zurich in 2017/18 she extended her gesture compositions linked to spatial movement. For nearly twenty years Franziska Baumann is composing for voice, disembodied voices linked to gestures in a scenario where she explores vocal presence and the role of the body with gesture-controlled live electronics in spatial performance art.

Keywords

Contemporary Vocal Art Practices, Performing Gestural Live Electronic Music, Interactive Staged Music Performance and Movement, Composing with 3D Ambisonic, Acousmatic and Disembodied Voice, Custom Musical Instrument (DIY), Digital Musical Instrument (DMI), Extended Vocal Techniques, STEIM, Sampling Practices for Vocal and Musical Improvisation, Improvisation and Real-Time Composition, Digital Score, Vocal Personas, Vocal Sound Dance, Imaginary Vocal Body, Aesthetiv of Uncertainty and In-Between, SensorGlove as Instrument and Body Extension

References

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